

THE INTERACTIVE CONTROL VINYL - IDVS+⁺

INTERACTIVE DIGITAL VINYL SYSTEM

FUNCTION

- ⊗ THE IDVS+ PRESENTS INFORMATIONS FROM LINKED AUDIO APPS ALONG WITH CORRESPONDING CONTROL INTERFACES
- ⊗ APPS AND PLAYBACK ARE CONTROLLED ACCORDING TO SENSORY POSITION DETECTION, ROTATION SPEED, PAD & TOUCH INPUTS
- ⊗ INPUTS MADE ON THE IDVS+ ARE SEND TO THE COMPUTER AND PROCESSED IN REAL TIME
- ⊗ THE COMPUTER SENDS INFORMATION TO THE IDVS+, WHICH IT THEN DISPLAYS IN REAL TIME
- ⊗ MULTI-TOUCH & TWO-HAND GESTURES TO OPERATE VIEWING-, CONTROL- AND PLAY-MODES
- ⊗ STATIC SCREENS ON DEMAND VIA VISUAL COUNTER ROTATION – RELATIVE TO TURNTABLE-ROTATION-SPEED

PLAYMODES AND CONTROLMODES

- ⊗ VARIOUS CONTROL INTERFACES AND PLAYBACK VISUALISATIONS FOR DIFFERENT TASKS
- ⊗ CIRCULAR AND LINE BASED UX/UI WITH & WITHOUT VISUAL COUNTER ROTATION OR SLOWMOTION EFFECT
- ⊗ **SWITCH-AREAS** INITIALICE A STATIC ROTARY-MENU TO CHOOSE AND SWITCH BETWEEN UI MODES

ADDITIONAL MODES

- ⊗ LIST MODE – TO NAVIGATE LIBRARIES, PLAYLISTS, ETC.
- ⊗ DJ GAME MODE – FOR MULTIPLE DJS
- ⊗ CONTROLLER EXTENSION MODE – FOR SEAMLESS EXPANSION OF DJ CONTROLLERS AND DJ PLAYERS
- ⊗ TRIGGER MODE – FOR SAMPLES
- ⊗ LOOP MODE – FOR EDITING AND PLAYING LOOPS
- ⊗ EDIT MODES – EDIT TRACKS, CUE POINTS, KEY, ETC.
- ⊗ CLOUD MODE – FOR AUDIO STREAMING SERVICES LIKE SPOTIFY, SOUNDCLOUD, ETC.
- ⊗ AMBIENT MODE – PRESENT VISUAL EFFECTS ON THE TURNTABLE

*VINYL MODE – A PHYSICALLY ACCURATE CONVERSION OF A TRACK'S WAVEFORM INTO THE PRINTIMAGE OF A RECORD, FOR AN OPTICAL ORIENTATION INSPIRED BY THE USER-EXPERIENCE WITH TRACKS ON REAL VINYL RECORDS

**ABSTRACT VINYL MODE – AN ABSTRACT VISUAL REPRESENTATION OF A TRACK'S WAVEFORM

FEATURES

- ⊗ WIRELESS SENSORIC DVS WITH CIRCULAR TOUCHSCREEN MONITORS, 12", BATTERY & NFC POWERED, NO NEEDLE REQUIRED
- ⊗ AUDIO- & DJ CONTROLLER FOR REAL-TIME INTERACTION WITH LINKED COMPUTERS / DJ-PLAYERS, TO BE USED ON (ROTATING) TURNTABLES
- ⊗ A POWERFULL AND VERSATILE DJ INTERFACE WITH LIMITLESS CONTROL OPTIONS ON TWO MULTITOUCH SURFACES
- ⊗ ***SWITCH-AREAS** TO GENTLY ACTIVATE CONTROL MODES, PREVENTING UNINTENDED CHANGES IN PLAYBACK SPEED BY TOUCH
- ⊗ EXPERIENCE AN ANALOG-LIKE PLAYBACK ON TURNTABLES, HAVING ALL YOUR DIGITAL TOOLS AND CONTENT DIRECTLY AT HAND

ADDITIONAL

- ⊗ BUILT IN VIBRATION-MOTOR FOR ADDITIONAL HAPTIC FEEDBACK TO USER INPUT
- ⊗ PRESSURE SENSITIVE TOUCHSCREENS WITH ROUGHENED SURFACE FOR BETTER FRICTION, SIMILAR TO A REAL VINYL RECORD
- ⊗ **TOUCHSCREEN II** SERVES ADDITIONALLY AS A PHYSICAL ****PAD BUTTON** FOR PRECISE CONTROL AT PRESS OR RELEASE
- ⊗ IN FUTURE BUILT AS A STANDALONE PLAYBACK DEVICE WITH WIRELESS AUDIO TRANSMISSION AND PLAYBACK FROM SSD / SD / CLOUD

